

Human-Centred mHealth Design: Survey on Perceptions, Skills, and Expectations

This questionnaire aims to understand your knowledge, experience, and expectations regarding software engineering, human-centered design, accessibility design, and mHealth application development before you begin the course. Your personal information will only be used to match the pre- and post-course surveys. Your responses will be analyzed and reported anonymously and in aggregate.

Section 1: Demographics

1. Gender: (choose one)
 - Male
 - Female
 - Non-binary / Third gender
 - Prefer not to say
2. Student ID (NIM): _____
3. Name: _____
4. Email: _____

Section 2: Perceptions and Attitudes Towards Human-Centred Software Design and Accessibility

1. I have a basic understanding of Human-Centred Software Design.
 - Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
2. I have a basic understanding of Software Accessibility Design.
 - Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
3. I understand the importance of designing for diverse user groups (e.g., older adults, people with disabilities).
 - Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree

4. I believe accessibility design is highly important in both software engineering education and industry.
 - Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree

Section 3: Individual Skills and Confidence

1. I am confident in conducting user research to identify user motivations, needs, and problems.
 - Not confident at All
 - Not confident
 - Neutral
 - Confident
 - Very confident
2. I am confident in applying design principles and including accessibility features in software design.
 - Not confident at All
 - Not confident
 - Neutral
 - Confident
 - Very confident
3. I have experience and confidence in creating design artefacts (e.g., personas, scenarios, prototypes) and conducting design evaluations (e.g., cognitive walkthrough).
 - Not confident at All
 - Not confident
 - Neutral
 - Confident
 - Very confident

Section 4: Academic Readiness and Study Journey

1. I expect this course to help me apply human-centred and accessibility design concepts to other Informatics Engineering courses and projects.
 - Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
2. I expect this course to prepare me to integrate human-centred and accessibility design considerations into my final-year project.

- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
2. I expect this course to improve my collaboration and communication skills in academic team-based projects, especially when addressing human-centred and accessibility design challenges.
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neutral
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree

Section 5: Learning Expectations (Open-Ended Questions)

1. What do you hope to learn from this course? Please explain in detail.
2. In your opinion, what aspects are most important when designing a mHealth application?